

REVIEW ON ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY AND MULTIVITAMINS BY USING CLEOME GYNANDRA PLANT EXTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Cleome gynandra (Capparaceae) is also known as spider plant. Cleome gynandra is an abundantly available species and grow in India and all over the world. In traditionally they are used for treating many diseases as well as act as a nutritional supplement or they have nutritional benefits. Cleome is the largest genus containing 601 species of ecological ethnobotanical and course of medicinal importance. In India 15 species and 12 are reported in Maharashtra state. In India alone it is used by the traditional healers for many diseases e.g. epilepsy, irritable bowel syndrome and in protozoal and worm infections. C. gynandra is typically well-known herb in southern Africa reaching out from the Limpopo, the North-West, Gauteng, the Northern Cape, and Namibia. Plant having such pharmacological activity such as anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antidiabetic, immunomodulator. In North - eastern region of india or in african region they used as a dietary supplement.

KEYWORDS: cleome gynandra, anti-inflammatory, nutritional benefit, Ayurveda, Morphology.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Herbs Information

Cleome gynandra L. is a plant native to Asia and sub-Saharan Africa and is present in tropical and subtropical areas all over the world (Adhikari and Paul. 2018). It is usually referred to as cats' whiskers, African spider flower or spider plant. Synonyms include *Gynandropsis gynandra* (L.) Briq., *Gymnogonia pentaphylla* (L.) R. Br. ex Steud. *Gynandropsis pentaphylla* Blanco., *Cleome pentaphylla* L., *Cleome pentaphylla* var. *glabra* Kuntze., *Pedicellaria pentaphylla* (L.) Schrank., *Pedicellaria pentaphylla* (L.) Schrank. *Pedicellaria triphylla* (L.) Pax. *Gynandropsis pentaphylla* (L.) DC. *Podogyne pentaphylla* (L.) *Cleome gynandra* (*Capparaceae*) is also known as spider plant. *Cleome gynandra* is an erect, annual or perennial herb. It is used as a medicinal plant and can be found in all over world. It grows as a weed in paddy fields and also in roadsides and in open grass lands.^[1] *C. gynandra* plant occurring throughout the tropics and subtropics of Africa. In South Africa, it is found in agricultural land and near human settlements. It is less common in areas with highly humid climate.^[2]

1.2. Global nutrition report^[3]

According to the United Nations (2019), the world population reached 7.7 billion in mid-2019 and is anticipated to reach 8.5 billion by 2030.

the world is facing the double burden of undernutrition (thinness, stunting and underweight) and overnutrition (obesity and overweight).

The 2021 Global Nutrition Report estimated that 149.2, 45.4 and 38.9 million children under five years are stunted, wasted and overweight, respectively. About 2.2 billion (40%) of both men and women are reported to be obese or overweight.

In 2024, Global Nutrition Report estimated 35 million children under the age of 5 years were overweight. Once considered a high-income country problem, overweight is on the rise in low- and middle-income countries. In Africa, the number of overweight children under 5 years has increased by nearly 12.1% since 2000. Almost half of the children under 5 years who were overweight or living with obesity in 2024 lived in Asia.

2. Description of Cleome Gynandra Plant

It is a tropical annual herb mainly used as a vegetables in Africa and Asia as a nutritional supplement. In India they are rarely used as painkillers or as anti-inflammatory by the traditional way. It is used as a medicinal plant or food source in most of the community.

2.1 Taxonomy of cleome gynandra^[5]

Kingdom: plantae

Division: angiosperms

Class: dicotyledone

Order: capparidales (capparales)

Family: Cleomaceae

Genus: Cleome

Species: gynandra

2.2 Chemical Constituents

The extract of cleome gynandra contain some phytochemicals such as Alkaloids, flavonoids (kaempeferol, quercetin, and isorhamnetin), phenols (gallic, caffeic, coumaric, sinapic, and ferulic acids), tannins, cardiac glycoside, saponins, terpenoids, anthraquinones. Cleome gynandra plant contain some vitamins like; provitamin A, vitamin B, vitamin C, vitamin E etc. and minerals like; calcium, iron, copper, cobalt, manganese, zinc, selenium, potassium, magnesium, and phosphorus etc. and fatty acids are present in seeds like; palmitic acid, steric acid, oleic acid, linioeic acid etc.

2.3 Phytochemicals Study Of Cleome Gynandra Plant^[6]

Phytochemicals content that is linked to antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, antimalarials, anticancer, nutritional value and phytochemical depend on production techniques used, environmental growing conditions, soil fertility and plant growth phase at harvest Cleome gynandra (wild spider plant) plant is specially known for C4 photosynthetic pathway which is an adaptational (adjustment to suit new condition) mechanisms.

3. Sanskrit synonyms^[7]

Ajagandha, Vastagandha - plant smells like a goat

Putigandha, Uragandha, Vigandhika, Pootikeeta, - Plant has unpleasant strong odor.

Barbaraka, Barbara, Pooti Barbara, Surapushpi, Kharapushpa, Shakambhara, Badaraka, Karavi, Tungi, Pooti Mayurika, Tilaparni – the leaves resemble to those of sesame leaves.

3.1 Ayurvedic reference

अजगन्धा कटुः पाके रसे रूक्षाग्निदीपनी ॥ १२०९॥
 हृद्या रुच्या लघुस्तीक्ष्णा दृक्शुक्रकफवातहा ॥१२१०॥ कै.नि.
 तिलपर्णी कटुस्तिक्ता विपाके कटुका लघुः ।
 अहिमा ग्राहिणी रुच्या शोफकुष्ठ कफापहा ॥६५४॥
 वह्निकृत् बादरं बीजं गुल्मानाहामशूलजित् ।
 उष्णवीर्यं कफहरं मारुतज्वरनाशनम् ॥ ६५५॥ कै.नि.
 अजगन्धा वातहरा वीर्योष्णा तु ज्वरापहा ।
 गुल्माष्ठीलाकफानाहशूलजिद्वह्निकृत्परा ॥१०८॥ ध.नि.
 पर्णाशस्तत्र कृष्णे तु कठिल्लककुठेरकौ ।
 तत्र शुक्लेऽर्जकः प्रोक्तो वटपत्रस्ततोऽपरः ॥ ५६॥
 बर्बरीत्रितयं रूक्षं शीतं कटु विदाहि च ।
 तीक्ष्णं रुचिकरं हृद्यं दीपनं लघुपाकि च ।
 पित्तलं कफवातास्रकण्डूकृमिविषापहम् ॥५७॥ भा.प्र.
 अजगन्धा कटूष्णा स्याद्वातगुल्मोदरापहा ।
 कर्णव्रणार्तिशूलघ्नी पीता चेदञ्जने हिता ॥१७८॥ रा.नि.

3.2 Ajagandha (Cleome gynandra) benefits according to Ayurveda^[8]

Vahnikrut, Agnideepani: Improves digestion strength
 Hrudyas: acts as cardiac tonic, congenial for heart
 Ruchy: improves taste, relieves anorexia.
 Druk: good for eyes
 Shukrahara: Aphrodisiac
 Kapha Vatahara: Balances Kapha and Vata Dosha.
 Grahi: absorbent, useful in diarrhea, IBS
 Kaphapaha: balances Kapha, useful in productive cough, asthma

Vatahara: useful in treating disorders of Vata Dosha imbalance such as neuralgia, paralysis, constipation, bloating, etc.

Pittals: Increases Pitta Dosha

3.3 Ayurvedic Properties of Cleome Gynandra Plant

Rasa (Taste) – Katu (Pungent)

Guna (Quality) – Teekshana (Sharp)

Veerya (Potency) – Ushna (Hot)

Vipaka (Post digestive effect) – Katu (Pungent).

Karma (Action) – Fruit – Balances the Vata and Pitta dosha.

Bark – Balances Kapha and Vata dosha.

Projyang (Part used) – Seeds, Leaves, Roots are used.

4. Morphology^[9]

4.1 Macroscopy Of Plant

Annual herb up to 250 - 260 cm tall; much branches and sometimes become woody with age

Stem

sticky with glandular hair

Leaves: palmately compound with 3-5 leaflets.

Leaf stalk is about 20 to 50 mm long with glandular hair.

Stalk are 20 to 100 × 8 to 40 mm smooth or with gland.

5. Botanical Characteristic of Cleome Gynandra^[10-12]

Wild spider plant under the genus of cleome that exists under the Cleomaceae family. the plant grown up to the 1.5 to 2 cm. Hight that can develop stout and branched stems. the stems can be green and violet to purple pigmentation.

Leaves

Leaves are oppositely arranged to the stems and attached petioles are 3 to 23 cm. Long. Shape of leaves in various form ovate elliptic to lanceolate - oblanceolate. Leaves have clear-green or dark green colours, finely round ends with sparsely but distinctly hairy surface. Surface area is about 2-10cm long and 2-4 cm wide. Spider plant are unisexual as well as bisexual. The bisexual type consists of stamen and carpel within the same flower hence the synonyms gynandropsis taken the synonyms gynandropsis taken from gynaphore (female)

and androphore (male) and in unisexual type consists of a reduced, non-functional or absence of female part of spider flower. The flower consists of four narrow petals which is white, pale pink in colour. Four sepals and six stamens having long purple filaments. The whole inflorescence is about 30 cm in length and flower is about 1 to 2.5 cm in a diameter.

As mentioned in fig 1

Seeds^[12]

Shape of seeds is thin and rough or thin and smooth 12cm long, 8 to 10 mm wide. Fruit is dry dehiscent and composed of two carpels.

Green and turns yellow when ripe to release many seed which are subglobose, gray to black, germinate at 31°C and at low of 12°C and high at 36°C.

(fig. 2: Stem with glandular hair)

(fig. 1: Leaves)

(Fig. 3: flower.)

(fig. 4: seeds)

6. Nutritional Composition

Fresh leaves of cleome gynandra contains

	Percentage of average %	Range
Moisture	84.94%	79.35%-88.8%
Proteins	3.9%-16.04% dry matter	3.9%-16.04%
ASH	5.88%	1.46%-18.71%
Crude fiber	7.58%	1.8%-22.10%
Lipids	2.56%	0.3%-6.50%
Carbohydrate	37.065%	13.1%-59.28%
Energy (kcal/100g)	152.88	46.61-280.32

Types of vitamins are present in cleome gynandra plant

TYPES OF VITAMINS	SUB TYPE	Mg/100g average	Range
Vitamin A	RAE	0.434	-
Provitamin A	α - carotene	0.05	-
	β -carotene	3.51	1.8-5.9
	β - cryptoxanthin	0.13	-
	Total carotenoids	104.67	77.2-162.3
Vitamin E	α - tocopherol	1.3	0.02-3.72
	γ - tocopherol	0.017	0.002-0.04
Vitamin B	Thiamine	0.06	-
	Riboflavin	0.145	0.08-0.21
	folate	0.121	-
Vitamin C	Total ascorbic acid	92.13	2-140
	Reduced ascorbic acid	108.14	94-119

7. Anti-inflammatory activity by using Cleome gynandra plant extracts^[13-17]

Anti-inflammatory agent is a drug or substance that reduces inflammation (redness, swelling, pain, and heat) by blocking the biochemical processes.

Cleome gynandra plant extracts used in treatment of inflammation. Lots of steroidal and non-steroidal and immunosuppressive drugs are used to reduce inflammatory symptoms and pain Diagram 5. Containing the highlights of anti-inflammatory activity of cleome gynandra.

Methanolic extracts of cleome gynandra leaves extracts contained biological activity component such as steroids, flavonoids, saponins, carbohydrates, phenols and glycosides which is used to reduce the arthritis induced by Freund's adjuvant in rats. Particularly the extract treated rat displayed a significant decrease in paw volume starting from 3rd week as compare to normal rat.

Hematological and biochemical parameters related to arthritis including haemoglobin, WBC, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, are restored to normal level. By using Cleome gynandra extracts treatment.

The activity of lysosomal enzyme and inflammatory cytokines observed in arthritis-induced rats, such as lactate dehydrogenase, alkaline phosphatase, aspartate transaminase, alanine transaminase, beta-glucuronidase, acid phosphate, cathepsin-D, TNF- α is reduced after the applying the treatment of C-gynandra extracts.

Mechanisms of Action: Cleome gynandra plant extracts showing NSAIDs activity and this NSAIDs inhibit the cyclooxygenase enzymes (**cox-1 and cox-2**).

(Fig. 5: Containing the highlights of anti-inflammatory activity of cleome gynandra)

CONCLUSION

Cleome gynandra is a widely utilized traditional medicinal plant known for its therapeutic potential in the treatment of various ailments, including rheumatism, bacterial infections, food poisoning, inflammation, and pain. The plant is a rich source of essential nutrients, particularly vitamin C, β -carotene, minerals, and proteins. Phytochemical investigations have revealed that extracts of C. gynandra exhibit diverse pharmacological activities, such as anticancer, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and cardioprotective effects. Owing to its

bioactive constituents and nutritional composition, *C. gynandra* holds promise for future development as a natural analgesic and multivitamin supplement in a single formulation

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